

Adsorption of Sodium Dodecyl Sulphate (NaDS) at Toluene-water Interface

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The adsorption of sodium dodecyl sulphate (NaDS) on toluene/water interface at 25° has been measured by the interfacial tension lowering method and the emulsion technique. The results obtained by the two methods agree within the limits of experimental error.

The data obtained appear to fit the adsorption isotherm of Freundlich and also that of Langmuir.

The adsorption of NaDS on air-water and oil-water interfaces has been investigated by a number of authors¹⁻⁷ using the method of measurement of lowering of interfacial tension combined with Gibbs equation. Cockbain⁵ and Groot⁹ have studied its adsorption at *n*-decane/water and at nujol/water interfaces respectively using two different methods. As measurements of adsorption by more than one method is very desirable we undertook the study of NaDS at toluene/water interface by two independent methods. One of them is based on the measurement of lowering of interfacial tension (γ) combined with Gibbs equation and the other is based on direct estimation of NaDS by a titration technique before and after dispersion of a given volume of toluene in a known volume of NaDS solution at constant ionic strength. The constant ionic strength has been maintained to avoid the theoretical controversy over the use of Gibbs adsorption isotherm.

From the first method we get the number of gm-ion of NaDS adsorbed per 1 cm² of the interface using Gibbs isotherm $\Gamma = -\frac{1}{RT} \frac{d\gamma}{d \log C}$. The use of Gibbs isotherm in this form is justified as in our experiment there has always been present a sufficient excess of added neutral electrolyte^{3,8,9}. The second method gives us the amount of the long chain ion adsorbed (x) on the total surface area (S) of the toluene globules formed by the dispersion of the same volume of oil in a given volume of aqueous solution of NaDS of

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known concentration. Assuming that total surface area (S) remains constant for a series of emulsions prepared exactly in the same way and kept under the same conditions, the applicability of different adsorption isotherms to these data could be tested.

EXPERIMENTAL

A toluene water emulsion has been prepared by using pure NaDS* (c.m.c. = 0.0079) as the ionic stabilizer. The toluene is of A.R. quality, E. Merck, and has been redistilled. In all our experiments double distilled water of specific conductance $\rho = 0.57 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ has been used. It has been found that NaDS in solution hydrolyses appreciably on keeping and so all the experiments have been done as quickly as possible.

Measurement of γ . In all our experiments γ has been measured by the ring method. The instrument is Du Noüy tensiometer, calibrated by standard pure liquids of known surface tension at a constant room temperature. The measurements have been carried out at two ionic strengths 0.1 and 0.01 maintained by adding pure NaCl. The data are recorded in the Table 1.

TABLE I

Concn. of NaDS in gm-mole/l $C \times 10^4$	Temperature = 25° $\gamma_0 = 36.0 \text{ dynes/cm}^2$.	
	Adsorbed amount in	Adsorbed amount in
	gm-ion/cm ²	gm-ion/cm ²
	(From Gibbs isotherm)	(From Gibbs isotherm)
	Ionic strength = 0.01	Ionic strength = 0.01
	$\Gamma \times 10^{11}$	$\Gamma \times 10^{11}$
0.054	—	8.33
0.072	—	9.21
0.091	6.31	10.5
0.180	7.71	13.3
0.274	9.13	—
0.360	9.69	16.7
0.46	10.50	17.5
0.54	—	18.4
0.91	13.7	—
1.83	16.7	—
2.74	18.4	—
3.00	19.3	—
3.50	20.2	—

* NaDS is a kind gift from Prof. K. J. Mysels.

Estimation of Γ . The surface excess Γ has been calculated by using the Gibbs isotherm in the form $\Gamma = \frac{1}{2.303 RT} \frac{d\gamma}{d \log C}$ for reasons explained previously. The values of $\frac{d\gamma}{d \log C}$ have been obtained from a graphical plot of γ against $\log C$ Fig. 1(a,b).

Fig. 1

Knowing the difference in concentration of NaDS in the aqueous phase before and after dispersion of toluene globules and the volume of aqueous phase, the total amount of adsorbed NaDS (x) on the toluene globules has been estimated. The data are recorded in the Tables II and III.

TABLE II

*Temperature = 25°**Ionic strength = 0.01*

Concn. of NaDS before dispersion $C \times 10^4$	Equilibrium Concn. of NaDS in gm-mole/l $C \times 10^4$	Total amount of NaDS adsorbed estimated in gm-ion $x_s \times 10^6$
2.74	2.51	4.6
1.83	1.62	4.2
0.91	0.74	3.4
0.462	0.33	2.64
0.361	0.24	2.42
0.271	0.16	2.22

TABLE III

Temperature = 25° Ionic strength = 0.1

5 ml. of toluene dispersed in 100 ml. of aqueous solution of NaDS

Concn of NaDS before dispersion in gm-mole/l $C \times 10^5$	Equilibrium concn. of NaDS in gm-mole/l $C \times 10^5$	Total amount of NaDS adsorbed in gm-ion/5 ml. of toluene dispersed $x_e \times 10^6$
4.0	2.18	1.82
3.6	1.81	1.79
2.8	1.13	1.67
2.7	1.14	1.56

From Gibbs isotherm we get Γ , the adsorbed amount of the long chain ion per 1 cm² of the interface. On the other hand, x , is the actual amount of long chain ion adsorbed on the total surface resulting from the dispersion of oil globules in the aqueous phase. Hence $x\alpha\Gamma$, i.e., $x = S\Gamma$ where S is the proportionality constant which is here obviously the total surface area. S has been found in this way for each of the emulsion and the data are recorded in the Tables IV and V.

TABLE IV

Ionic strength = 0.01

Γ (from Gibbs isotherm) $\times 10^{11}$ gm-ion/cm ²	Total amount of NaDS adsorbed estimated in gm-ion/10 ml of toluene dispersed $x_e \times 10^6$	Total surface area in cm ² $S \times 10^{-4}$	Estimated adsorp- tion on surface area $S_a = 2.68 \times 10^4$ cm ² $x \times 10^6$
18.1	4.6	2.54	4.8
15.9	4.2	2.64	4.25
12.7	3.4	2.68	3.4
9.1	2.64	2.90	2.37
8.5	2.42	2.85	2.25
7.7	2.22	2.88	2.04

TABLE V

Ionic strength = 0.1

Γ (from Gibbs isotherm) $\times 10^{11}$ gm-ion/cm ²	Total amount of NaDS adsorbed estimated in gm-ion/5 ml. of toluene dispersed $x_e \times 10^6$	Total surface area in cm ² $S \times 10^{-4}$	Estimated adsorption on surface area $S_f = 1.38 \times 10^4$ cm ² $x \times 10^6$
	10.8	1.56	1.44
10.8	1.67	1.54	1.50
13.0	1.79	1.38	1.79
13.0	1.82	1.33	1.89

DISCUSSION

It may be noticed from the data recorded in Table I that the values of Γ at first increases and then tends to become constant at a certain level close to the saturation value. The saturation values can only be obtained by the extrapolation of the curves. For ionic strengths 0.01 and 0.1 the interface becomes nearly saturated at 3.5×10^{-4} gm-ion/l and 5.4×10^{-5} gm-ion/l of NaDS respectively. The effect of increasing the ionic strength is to increase the adsorption of the long chain ion markedly. This is also supported by the data recorded in the Tables II and III obtained by emulsion analysis. At ionic strength 0.01 the adsorbed amount of NaDS per ml. of toluene dispersed is 4.6×10^{-7} gm-ion when the concentration of NaDS in the aqueous phase is 2.51×10^{-4} gm-ion/l; while at ionic strength 0.1 that per ml. of toluene is 3.6×10^{-7} gm-ion when the concentration of NaDS in the aqueous phase is 2.2×10^{-5} gm-ion/l.

We notice from the data recorded in the Tables IV and V that over the range of concentrations of NaDS investigated for the two ionic strengths the total surface area varies slightly. To test the applicability of the different adsorption isotherms the surface area must have a fixed value; $S_f = 1.38 \times 10^4$ cm² for ionic strength 0.1 and $S_f = 2.68 \times 10^4$ cm² for ionic strength 0.01 have been chosen from the Tables IV and V. The amount adsorbed on S_a has been estimated in the following way. $x = \frac{x_e \times S_a}{S}$, where x is the corrected value of total adsorption for surface area S_f , x_e that has been found experimentally for surface area S for the particular emulsion.

Applicability of Freundlich¹⁰ and Langmuir¹¹ isotherms. Freundlich isotherm may be written in the form

$$\log x = \frac{1}{\nu} \log C + \log k$$

where x is the adsorbed amount on a given surface area S_f and C is the equilibrium concentration, ν and k being the constants characteristic of the system. A plot of $\log x$ vs $\log C$ yields a straight line for each of the ionic strengths used Fig. 2(a,b). It may, therefore, be concluded that Freundlich isotherm holds over the range of concentrations of NaDS investigated at the toluene-water interface.

Fig. 2

Vold and Groot¹² and later on Ghosh¹³ have shown that Langmuir isotherm can be verified experimentally by plotting $1/x$ against $1/C_f$ where C is the equilibrium concentration and f is the mean activity coefficient. This isotherm has been tested using the corrected values of adsorption on S_f and plotting $1/x$ against $1/C_f$ Fig. 3(a,b). A straight line over the range of concentrations of NaDS investigated is obtained for each of the two ionic strengths used. We may, therefore, conclude that Langmuir isotherm also holds over the range of concentrations of NaDS investigated.

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